

Mark's σπεκουλάτωρ and the Origin of his Gospel

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Abstract

In Mark, Herod Antipas orders John the Baptist's execution by a σπεκουλάτωρ. Thus, Mark becomes the first witness to the use of the word σπεκουλάτωρ in Greek. The Latin word *speculator* was used in the 1st century mainly in respect of the praetorian *speculatores* soldiers who acted as the emperor's personal guard in Rome and who were involved in the events of the civil war in the years 68-70 CE. Mark's use of the word σπεκουλάτωρ (along with other factors) points to the city of Rome as the gospel's origin, since the vast majority of attestations of the word *speculator* occur in the city of Rome, where these soldiers mainly carried out their duties.

Key words

speculator, Latinisms, praetorian soldiers, Gospel of Mark, Roman army

1 Introduction

Mark narrates that Herod Antipas ordered the execution of John the Baptist in the context of a feast, although he does not indicate where the event took place (Mk 6.17-29). The death of John the Baptist at the hands of Antipas is also related by Josephus, who places the event in Machaerus (*A.J.* 18.119). In Mark's account, Antipas orders a σπεκουλάτωρ to bring him the head of John the Baptist.

²⁷ καὶ εὐθὺς ἀποστείλας ὁ βασιλεὺς σπεκουλάτορα ἐπέταξεν ἐνέγκαι τὴν κεφαλὴν αὐτοῦ. καὶ ἀπελθὼν ἀπεκεφάλισεν αὐτὸν ἐν τῇ φυλακῇ ²⁸ καὶ ἤνεγκεν τὴν κεφαλὴν αὐτοῦ ἐπὶ πίνακι καὶ ἔδωκεν αὐτὴν τῷ κορασίῳ, καὶ τὸ κοράσιον ἔδωκεν αὐτὴν τῇ μητρὶ αὐτῆς.

²⁷ So he immediately sent a *speculator* with orders to bring John's head. He went, beheaded John in the prison, ²⁸ and brought back his head on a platter. He presented it to the girl, and she gave it to her mother.

The word σπεκουλάτωρ is clearly a loanword from the Latin *speculator*. It is a Latin word used in a Greek discourse. This word is neither translated nor explained, unlike some Aramaic words such as αββα ὁ πατήρ (Mk 14.36) or the codeswitchings with Aramaic (e.g., εφραθα, ὃ ἐστὶν διανοίχθητι Mk 7.34)¹. The word σπεκουλάτωρ is not attested in Greek before Mark and remains rare until the third century. Many English versions translate the word σπεκουλάτωρ as 'executioner', 'a soldier of his guard', 'one of his guard'. But these translations are misinterpretations and misleading, since σπεκουλάτωρ does not mean a soldier of Antipas' guard, let alone executioner².

¹ Codeswitching: the change of language in the same speech act. It is a linguistic strategy in which expressions from a different language are used within a discourse in a matrix language. It can convey important social meanings above and beyond the referential content of a word or utterance. Cf. Gardner-Chloros 2009.

² It is translated as executioner in Lührmann 1987: 113, as a soldier of Herod's guard in Gnilka 1978: 249 and in Pesch 1976: 341. Other commentators assume that its meaning could be executioner: Lagrange 1929: 162; Focant 2012: 251; Guelich 1989: 325, 333.

No commentary or dictionary has carried out a serious examination of this word³. Many authors rely on Henry Cadbury and Helmut Köster, who maintain that Mark's Latinisms would have been widely known throughout the Roman Empire⁴. Cadbury's evidence for this claim is that all of these words occur in Aramaic or late Hebrew⁵. But this does not demonstrate that the word was known in the first century, since the attestations of ספקלָטוֹר in Sifre Num. 11.15 (§ 91) 25a; Lev. Rab. 26.2 (124a); Tg. Neoph. Gen. 37.36, 43.3-4, 41.10-13 and b.Sabb. 108a are very late and do not reflect Mark's context. Important commentaries that give attention to Mark's Latinisms such as Bas M. F. Van Iersel's and Robert Gundry's do not analyse σπεκουλάτωρ⁶. Some commentaries do indeed point out that it is a Latinism but their analysis is very superficial⁷. Other authors analyse the word, but confuse its meaning, as well as the functions performed by these soldiers at different times⁸. Many authors rely on the brief analysis of Harold Hoehner, who cites Adrian Sherwin-White and Emil Schürer⁹. No author has developed a sociolinguistic analysis of Mark's Latin words which is necessary to identify the functions they may have developed and the connotations they may have evoked¹⁰, because an integrated loanword would not attract the attention of its listeners, whereas a non-integrated loanword would.

This article proposes that Mark's use of the word σπεκουλάτωρ (along with other factors) points to the city of Rome as the origin of his gospel, since the vast majority of attestations of the Latin word *speculator* occur in the city of Rome, where these soldiers mainly carried out their duties.

In order to demonstrate this proposal, we will first highlight the semantic and sociolinguistic considerations behind it. First, language-contact situations generate various phenomena, such as borrowing and codeswitching, which develop different functions (Section § 2). Most words are polysemous, and the context of their usage selects the 'one sense' that is intended from the various senses of which the word is capable (§ 3). Third, meanings of words evolve, as do their referents (§ 4). Fourth, the meaning of a word must be analysed in its literary context (§ 5) and in its historical context (§ 6). Fifth, it is necessary to know the semantic field of a word in order to understand it (§ 7). Sixth, a word's meaning is negotiated between the author and the reader. Seventh, meaning representation is encyclopaedic, since words are 'points of access' to vast repositories of knowledge relating to a particular concept (§ 8).

³ Dictionaries analyse the word in a brief and confusing way. Moulton and Milligan 1929: 582; Liddell, Scott and Jones 1996: 626; Balz and Schneider 1990 3.263; Bauer 2000: 832; Montanari 2015: 1944; Dickey 2023: 442.

⁴ These are precisely those (Latin words) which would be adopted outside of Italy in any of the Greek-speaking provinces of the Roman Empire'. Cadbury 1958: 88-89. 'Latinisms could occur at any place where a Roman garrison was stationed and Roman administration of a province was established'. Köster 1982: 171. Also Zahn 1909: 489. In general, scholars simply repeat various clichés about Mark's Latinisms, lumping them together. This is erroneous since some of the Latinisms were already integrated into koine Greek (δηνάριον, μόδιος), while others (πραγελλόω, σπεκουλάτωρ) had not been attested.

⁵ Cadbury 1958: 89. Cf. Jastrow 1886-1903: 1017; Krauss 1899: 92-93, 409; Strack and Billerbeck 1924: 12; Levy and Fleischer 1876: 573. This word does not appear in the Mishnah.

⁶ Van Iersel 1998: 222; Gundry 1993: 305.

⁷ Taylor 1972: 316-317; Swete 1898: 127.

⁸ Collins 2007: 314; Marcus 2000: 397.

⁹ Hoehner 1972: 119-120. Sherwin-White 1963: 109-110, asserts that, according to Tacitus, these soldiers appear at times of military intrigue. Schürer, Vermes, Millar, Goodman and Black 2014: 371.

¹⁰ Thorough discussions of Mark's Latinisms can be found in Von Bendemann 2011, Bedenbender 2013: 281-286, Lamas 2020: 11-23; but none of them specifically studies the word σπεκουλάτωρ. Zeichmann 2017, despite the title of his article, is not a sociolinguistic study and does not analyse this word.

Having detailed these considerations, we now turn to the nine questions guiding the constructive proposal of this article. What kind of word is σπεκουλάτωρ from a sociolinguistic point of view? (§ 2). Which were the meanings of the Latin word *speculator*? (§ 3). When does the word *speculator* refer specifically to Roman soldiers? (§ 4). What does the word σπεκουλάτωρ mean in its Markan context? (§ 5). To whom does Mark refer by this word: to a Roman soldier or to a soldier of Antipas? Is it plausible that in 30 CE there was a Roman *speculator* alongside Antipas? (§ 6). Why did Mark use a Latin word when he had other Greek words related to the semantic field of soldiers at his disposal? (§7). How would this word be interpreted by a Greco-Roman audience? (§ 8). Can this word help to illuminate where the gospel was written¹¹? (§ 9).

2 Sociolinguistic analysis of the word σπεκουλάτωρ

The first question to address is what kind of word is σπεκουλάτωρ from a sociolinguistic point of view? In Mk 6.27 σπεκουλάτωρ is a masculine noun appearing in the accusative. This word comes from the Latin *speculator* and has been phonetically and morphosyntactically adapted to Greek. According to Shana Poplack's 'variationist theory' this adaptation implies that σπεκουλάτωρ is a nonce-borrowing, while for Carol Myers-Scotton it would be a case of 'single word switch'¹². In either case, it is a Latin word used in Mark's Greek discourse.

Mark is the first witness to the presence of the word σπεκουλάτωρ in Greek. Neither Matthew nor Luke retain it for their versions of the pericope. Its absence in Matthew is significant because he uses most of Mark's Latinisms¹³. The next attestation of σπεκουλάτωρ occurs in a papyrus of the 2nd century: P.Mich. 8.469.22. This papyrus was written in Latin, but on its verso the addressee of the letter (*Claudi[us] Tiberia*) appears in Greek: Κλαυδίω [Τιβεριανῶ] σπεκουλ(άτορι)¹⁴. This papyrus was found at Karanis, near Alexandria and is dated 100-125 CE. There are no further attestations in the 2nd century. In the 3rd century, four attestations are found in the papyri: P.Isid. 32.9; P. Bodl. 1.166.11, 19 and SB 18.13946. Its presence is noteworthy in P.Yale.Inv. 1536. col. 2 = CPJ 2.159A, a papyrus containing part of the *Acta Appiani*. It is a literary version of a trial that may have taken place in Rome, but it is not an official document. It narrates the trial of Appianus, γυμνασίαρχος of Alexandria before the emperor Commodus. It is surprising that several modern translations render σπεκουλάτωρ as 'executioner'. In the 3rd century only two attestations are found in inscriptions: σπεκλάτωρ in BuEp 1959.260 (II-III CE, Tomis) = AE 1960.348 = SEG 18.301 and σπεκλάτορι κεντρο[υρίωνι in SEG 60.1547 (250 CE, Oinoanda) = AE 2010.164. In the 4th century it is attested 30 times in the papyri, among others: P.Oxy. 9.1193.1; P.Oslo 2.59.9; P.Oxy. 9.1223; P.Erl. 27. It also appears in the inscription I.Klaudiupolis 19.10 (Bithynia) = AE 1987.920 possibly from the 4th century CE. An undated inscription is IGLS 6.2980 (Beqaa, Syria), where it appears as σπ[ε]κ[ου]λάτορος. One literary text that attests σπεκουλάτωρ is Secundus the

¹¹ There are three proposals for where Mark's Gospel was written: 1) Rome, defended by Hengel 1985: 28-30 and Van Iersel 1998: 31-41. 2) Marxsen 1956: 142 broke the consensus on Rome with his proposal of Galilee, also advocated by Roskam 2004. 3) Syria is proposed by Theissen 1989: 246-251 and Marcus 2000: 33-37. A summary of the arguments in favor of each location can be found at Garland 2015: 70-80.

¹² Nonce borrowing: words attested only once, usually adapted to the target language. They are the most common product in language contact situations. Poplack 2018: 79. Single word switch: a word from another language that appear once attested in a corpus, but shows minimal adaptation. According to Myers-Scotton, they can be adapted to the receiving language. Myers-Scotton 2006: 254. Swain (2002: 130-136) reflects on the distinction between borrowed terms and codeswitching following Myers-Scotton.

¹³ Only κεντυρίων and ξέστης are not received in Matthew's gospel.

¹⁴ Cf. 'Code-Switching in the Subscriptio of Letters', in Adams 2003: 396-399, with several Greek and Latin examples.

philosopher's *Vita Secundi* 72.13, but this is late¹⁵. This analysis leads us to conclude that σπεκουλάτωρ in the 1st century is a nonce-borrowing from Latin. It is therefore a Latin word inserted in a Greek text.

3 The Latin word *speculator*

To understand the meaning of σπεκουλάτωρ in Mark's account, it is necessary to examine the Latin word *speculator*. The first aspect to highlight is that the word *speculator* is polysemic and its meaning has evolved over time¹⁶. Which were the meanings of the word *speculator*?

The primary meaning of *speculator* is observer, watchman, sentinel, spy¹⁷. It is found in Cicero, where it has the meaning 'observer of nature' (*Nat. d.* 1.83) and 'watchman of a ship' in Ovid, *Trist.* 3.9.10. Also in Cicero it has the meaning of 'observer' or 'spy' (*Verr.* 2.5.2.164-166) and in Ovid, *Am.* 1.9.16. When Varro uses the word, he means 'observer' or 'scout' (*Ling.* 6.82). In a non-military context it refers to someone who spies on other people's activities. It appears with this meaning in Cicero, *Div. Caec.* 51 and Livy, *Ab urbe cond.* 45.19.8. It can also refer to a sentinel or watchman (Cicero, *Nat. d.* 2.140, Seneca, *Nat.* 4b.6.2; Livy, *Ab urbe cond.* 31.24.4). Most instances of the word operating with this broader meaning occur in the 1st century BCE.

In a military context, a *speculator* was a scout, a spy, someone sent to observe the enemy. Thus in Sallust, *Jug.* 101.1 and 106 (written in 41-40 BCE), the word *speculatores* refers to scouts of Gaius Marius' army. In Nepos, *Alcib.* 8 (100-25 BCE) *speculatores* are scouts of the Athenian army¹⁸. In Cicero it has the meaning of military spy in *Leg. man.* (16) 46. In Julius Caesar and Livy *speculator* is used to designate scouts and spies both of the Roman army and other armies. In the context of the Roman army, *speculator* initially designated a group of soldiers of the legions in charge of the surveillance of the enemy (Julius Caesar). Later during the principate, the word referred to a soldier with a rank close to centurion who carried out different operations related to military intelligence. Specifically, it was used to designate two types of soldiers: the legionary *speculatores* and the praetorian *speculatores*. In the late 1st century CE the praetorian *speculatores* were no longer charged with protecting the emperor and by the 2nd century the *speculatores* had become officials of the governor in charge of justice and also acted as couriers.

4 The evolution of the word *speculator* and the *speculatores* soldiers

When does the word *speculator* refer specifically to Roman soldiers? How did the functions and the role of these *speculatores* evolve?

4.1 1st century BCE

¹⁵ Secundus lived in the 2nd century CE and an anonymous ancient biography about him is preserved in a fragment of a papyrus of the 3rd century CE. The complete edition of this biography comes from the 11th century. *Vita Secundi* 72.13: μετεκαλέσατο δέ τινα σπεκουλάτορα Ἑλληνα. σπεκουλάτωρ also appears in 72.16; 72.20; 74.4; 74.7.

¹⁶ Glare 2012: 1987; Lewis and Short 1955: 1739.

¹⁷ *Speculator* comes from *specio*, -ere, to watch, to observe. Vaan 2008: 578. The usual form of the word is *speculator*. Skånland discusses the different spellings *speculator* and *spiculator*. Skånland 1963.

¹⁸ Other attestations in Vergil, *Aeneid.* 12.346 where he refers to an army scout. Q. Curtius Rufus, *Hist.* 3.8.17-18; 4.9.1; 4.10.9; 6.4.14, where *speculatores* are scouts and explorers of Alexander the Great's army.

In the 1st century BCE, several authors deploy the word *speculator* in reference to Roman soldiers. Especially significant are the attestations in Julius Caesar, a coin minted by Mark Antony, and the attestations in Livy. Inscriptions where the word *speculator* appears are scarce at this time. Each of these warrants detailed discussion here.

The first instances of the word *speculatores* as soldiers of the Roman army appear in Julius Caesar's writings¹⁹. In the *Gallic Wars* (50 BCE) they are only mentioned twice, *BGall.* 2.11.2 and 5.49.8. They are soldiers who fulfill functions similar to the *exploratores*. They are not an organized unit. In the *Civil War*, they watch the movements of the enemy (*BCiv.* 3.66.1, 3.67.1). In the *African War* the *speculatores* are attached to Julius Caesar and quickly prepared to serve him (*BAfr.* 37.1, 31.4). Their other functions included transmitting orders (*BAfr.* 31.4) and performing reconnaissance tasks (*BHisp.* 28.1, 38; *BAfr.* 12, 35). If the *speculatores* were arrested they were executed (*BHisp.* 13 and 20), which is an indication of their importance.

An important attestation of the word is found on the coin minted by Mark Antony: RRC 544/12 (32 BCE). Reconnaissance was so essential and so risky to Roman field marshals that their reconnoitering force (i.e., the *speculatores*), became their bodyguards²⁰. Mark Antony formed his *speculatores* into a distinct *cohors*, which he honored with a coin in 32-31 BCE (COHORTIS SPECULATORUM²¹). By dedicating a coin to these soldiers, Antony attempted to win their support for his cause and demonstrate the strength he had at his disposal. Another coin minted by Antony at the same time (RRC 544/1, 544/8) bears the legend C(O)HORTIUM PRAETORIARUM, indicating that *speculatores* and praetorians were two separate units at this time²².

The recurrences of the word *speculator* are extensive (34x) in Livy (59 BCE-17 CE), who uses the word with three meanings: 1) in a broad sense, an observer; 2) to refer to scouts, spies, intelligence agents and 3) to the soldiers in charge of these tasks, both of the Roman army and those of the enemy (24x)²³. Seven of these attestations refer to *speculatores* of the Roman army (*Ab urbe cond.* 3.40.13; 9.23.3; 9.24.11; 27.15.1; 28.1.9; 28.2.2; 30.4.6). Sometimes he uses the words *exploratores* and *speculatores* interchangeably (for example, in 30.4.6 he names some army spies *speculatores* but shortly thereafter, in 30.5.1, he refers to the same spies as *exploratores*). Eight attestations are related to naval reconnaissance (22.19.5; 30.10.6; 30.10.14; 35.26.9; 35.38.14; 36.41.7; 36.42.8; 36.43.2). One *speculator* informs the Romans about Perseus' plans (42.13.1), and another is related to the observation of Attalus at Rhyme (45.19.8).

¹⁹ Julius Caesar's use of the term *speculator* detailed in Ezov 1996 and Austin and Rankov 1995: 56-58.

²⁰ These bodyguards are called *speculatores*, a name that betrays their origin. Speidel 1994: 21, 102. Also the *speculatores*, according to their original purpose, bodyguards of the governor, will have existed at the time of the late Republic as an elite troop of the *cohors praetoria*. They take their name from their purpose to protect the commander during his reconnaissance rides. Since the commander of the *exercitus provinciae* was deprived of the *cohors praetoria* in the imperial period, the *speculatores* would be taken from the legions and given the rank above the *beneficarii*. Domaszewski and Dobson 1981: 73.

²¹ BMC/RR 185 (East). CRR 1214 (4). RRC 544/12. RCV 1484. The coin depicts a warship, which shows that they were also used in naval operations. (Vegetius, *De re militari* 4.37.6 and Polybius, *Hist.* 3.96). Livy talks about ships *speculatoriae* (Livy, *Ab urbe cond.* 22.19.5; 30.10.6; 30.10.14; 35.26.9; 35.38.14; 36.41.7; 36.42.8; 36.43.2). Lammert 1929: 1584.

²² Bingham 2013: 182. Cowan 2014: 13-14.

²³ Military spies in 4.32.10 (Etruscans); 4.46.9; 21.53.11; 22.33.1 and 27.27.3 (Carthage); 30.23.5; 30.29.2; 34.61.12; 37.11.1; 40.5.12; 42.13.1; 42.26.3. Perseus and Demetrius spies (40.7.4; 40.7.6; 40.7.7; 40.14.6; 40.14.10).

The word *speculator* appears widely attested in inscriptions, especially in the 2nd and 3rd centuries CE. The inscriptions, unlike the literary sources, provide little information about the activities of *speculatores* in the early imperial period. Only four inscriptions attest the term in the 1st century BCE. Two appear in Italy: AE 1956.75²⁴ (44-1 BCE) and AE 1991.488 (50-1 BCE), one in Dalmatia CIL 3.2915 (30 BCE-9 CE) and one in Hispania (IRPPalencia 49).

4.2 1st century CE

With Augustus, two significant changes relating to the *speculatores* took place. Firstly, when Augustus reorganized the army, he formally institutionalized *speculatores* within the military, as specialized units within the legion²⁵. These legionary *speculatores* had various duties related to military intelligence, such as being couriers for the governor. Secondly, Augustus formed a guard of *speculatores* (the *speculatores Augusti* or *speculatores Caesari*²⁶) in addition to his newly created praetorian cohorts²⁷. Eventually the phrase *speculatores Caesari* became just *speculatores*²⁸. Individually, these *speculatores Caesari* remained attached to their legionary centuries and cohorts, but collectively they formed a separate body²⁹. The *speculatores Augusti* were elite praetorian horsemen whose weapon was the lance. The *speculatores Augusti*, performed various functions, among them the protection of the emperor (see Suetonius, Josephus³⁰), arrests, espionage, couriers³¹, even executions (see Seneca). These *speculatores* apparently held an important position in the gubernatorial *praetorium*³². The importance of the *speculatores* compared with the other praetorian soldiers is indicated by the fact that their *centurio* was placed ahead of the centurions *cohortis praetoriae*, *cohortis vigilum* and *legionis*. Therefore, in Augustus' time, the term *speculator* was used as a technical term to refer to two groups of soldiers already differentiated in the 1st century: the *speculatores* of the legions and the *speculatores* of the *praetorium* (*speculatores Augusti* or *Caesari*).

Starting under Tiberius in 23 CE, when all the praetorian cohorts were quartered in the *castra praetoria* on the outskirts of Rome³³ (Suetonius, *Aug.* 49.1), the *speculatores* were integrated into the praetorian cohorts as part of the praetorian guard and were no longer considered part of

²⁴ *speculator / legion(is) IIII Macedoniae*.

²⁵ Thus, *exploratores* are mounted scouts, sent to observe the enemy and reconnoiter the terrain, while *speculatores* act as intelligence couriers and clandestine agents. They act in pairs or alone.

²⁶ The first attestation of the *speculatores praetorii* appears on the coinage minted by Mark Antony and in a testimony of Suetonius who states that Augustus stayed at the house of one of his *speculatores* (Suetonius, *Aug.* 74.1). Clauss 1973: 46. When Augustus became the first ruler of the Empire in 27 BCE, he decided that such training was useful not only in war, but also in politics. Thus, from the ranks of the legions of all the provinces, Augustus recruited the Praetorian Guard. At this time the legions were increasingly made up of people from the provinces while the imperial guard was essentially Italian. Domaszewski and Dobson 1981: 19.

²⁷ The Praetorian soldiers were the only armed force in Italy. During the republic the Roman troops were not authorized to enter Rome. With Augustus, the presence of the Praetorians in the city is one of the signs that the situation has changed. Bingham 2013: 1.

²⁸ Bingham 2013: 89.

²⁹ Rankov and Hook 1994: 8. There are two positions among scholars: Durry 1938: 108-110, sees the *speculatores* as an elite group within the Praetorian Guard. It was a rank to which one could gain access after a few years of service. Passerini 1939: 70-73, sees the *speculatores* as an autonomous organised body, attached to their cohorts, in which they formed a special corps.

³⁰ Josephus suggests that the guard of a general was composed of *speculatores* (*B.J.* 3.127; 5.47).

³¹ Surely *speculatores* were used by Sejanus in his correspondence with Tiberius between Rome and Capri. Bingham 2013: 90.

³² Thus, in Tacitus, *Hist.* 2.1 and 2.22 they are named separately from the praetorian cohorts and the *equites speculatores*.

³³ Augustus did not allow more than three praetorian cohorts in Rome.

the emperor's guard³⁴. They depended on the *praefectus praetorio*, a prominent person of enormous political importance³⁵. Thus in Tiberius' time, *speculatores* was used as a technical term to refer primarily to the praetorian *speculatores* soldiers charged with the protection of the emperor and secondarily to refer to the *speculatores* of the legions. Of the *speculatores* of the legions and their activities we have very little information since their activities were covert.

Three attestations of the word in Seneca (4 BCE-65 CE) are significant, since he uses the word *speculator* both in a broad sense (*Ira* 3.36.2) and to refer to *speculatores* carrying out executions (*Ira* 1.18.4 and *Ben.* 25), which fits with Mark's account. Although Seneca testifies that *speculatores* were in charge of two executions, it does not follow that the meaning of the word is executioner, since by the same logic all other functions performed by *speculatores* would have to be accepted as meanings.

The *speculatores* were part of the praetorian guard and both corps played a leading role in the civil war known as the Year of the Four Emperors (68-69 CE). Praetorian tribunes were involved in the Pisonian conspiracy against Nero (Tacitus, *Ann.* 15.49). The praetorian prefects defected and persuaded the rank-and-file praetorians to follow them, which was a contributing factor to Nero's suicide. Galba received the support of the praetorian prefect Nymphidius and the praetorian guard to gain access to power after Nero. Galba disappointed and angered the praetorians by not paying them a promised donation. Otho ended Galba's rule with a conspiracy involving his praetorian *speculatores* (Tacitus, *Hist.* 1.25.1)³⁶. Vitellius formed a new praetorian guard from his Germanic legionaries, but Otho's ex-praetorians were partisans of Vespasian who fought against them. The praetorian guard contributed to Domitian's downfall. They besieged Nerva in his palace and demanded that he be handed over to those who had murdered Domitian, such that he deliver a speech in their support (Dio Cassius, *Hist. rom.* 68.3). This caused Trajan to succeed him as emperor. According to Michael Speidel, these praetorians would have been *speculatores*³⁷. Trajan adopted a new personal guard and wanted to execute the praetorians who had mutinied against Nerva (Dio Cassius, *Hist. rom.* 68.5.4). All these intrigues are reflected in the literary authors of the 2nd century CE, such as Tacitus and Suetonius; these will be detailed below.

In the 1st century CE there are 36 attestations of the word *speculator* in inscriptions³⁸ and one attestation in a papyrus from Egypt (ChLA. 1.7.a.b.9 [81-90 CE]³⁹). Of these 36 earlier attestations before 100 CE, 30 are from Italy (10 from Rome) and only 6 are from other provinces⁴⁰. Thus only 17% of surviving attestations of the word appear in inscriptions outside of Italy in the 1st century. Of these 36 attestations before 100 CE, 6 refer specifically to

³⁴ Ottley 2009: 52-53. According to Bingham this must have occurred under Vitellius, as they had fought with Otho and for them to continue as an independent unit could have been dangerous. Bingham 1997: 136.

³⁵ Speidel 1994: 34. Diploma CIL 16.21 (76 CE) distinguishes *speculatores* from praetorians. Sheldon 2005: 167.

³⁶ Cf. Ottley 2009: 94-107.

³⁷ Speidel 1994: 43.

³⁸ In the great majority of the attestations the word appears transcribed as *speculator*, although with the spelling *speclator* 7 attestations are found, of which only one is dated to the 1st century CE: CIL 6.8583 [I CE, Rome]. Other attestations of *speclator* in Lazio: CIL 10.8056.337a, .337b, 338b, 338c, 338e, CIL 15.5602 (Rome).

³⁹ The papyrus uses the terms *speculator* and *speclator*. A detailed description of the 'language use in the army in Egypt' in Adams 2003: 599-623.

⁴⁰ Attestations of *speculator* in the provinces: CIL 3.2915 (30 BCE-9 CE, Dalmatia). IRPPalencia 49 (27 BCE-14 CE, Hispania). CIL 13.6884 (1-30 CE, Germania): *spec/ulator leg(ionis)*. AE 2008.855 (1-50 CE, Galia). AE 1969/70.420 (73 CE, Germania). CIL 16.21 = CIL 3.853 (76 CE, Moesia, Serbia). Also CIL 3.4843 (1-200 CE, Noricum): *speculatoribus Caesaris Aug(usti)*. CIL 3.5223 (51-130, Noricum): (*centurio speculatorum Aug(usti)*). AE 1957.163 (201-250 CE, Pannonia): *ex pra/etorio ex / speculator*. Claus 1973: 52-53, 149.

*speculatores praetoriani*⁴¹ and 5 to *speculatores* of the legions⁴². Most of the inscriptions specify the cohort and *centuria* to which they belong, though a few only specify the *centuria*. With the exception of AE 1900.2 (II CE, Italy), where it is noted that a *speculator* dies in Faleris (Italy), there no other attestation of the *speculatores'* activities outside of Rome. The inscriptions from Italy do not report the place of activity of that *speculator*, but only where he resided when he died⁴³. The inscriptions reflect how the *speculatores* appear linked to Caesar and Rome.

4.3 2nd century CE

In the 2nd century, the word *speculator* appears 11 times in Tacitus (55-120 CE), who writes between 100 and 110 CE. Most of the attestations in Tacitus appear to refer to the praetorian *speculatores* in the year of the four emperors and deal with the intrigues in which they were protagonists, especially with Galba and Otto (*Hist.* 1.24.2; 1.25.1; 1.27.2; 1.31.1; 1.35.2; 1.43.2; 2.11.3; 2.33.3). Attestations about the *speculatores* of the legions also appear (*Ann.* 2.12.1⁴⁴; *Hist.* 3.43.2; 2.73.1). The case of *Hist.* 2.73.1 is significant since he narrates how *speculatores* of the legions of Syria and Judea carried news to Vitellius in Rome.

In Suetonius' *Life of the Caesars* (70-126 CE) five attestations appear. In *Aug.* 27.4 the word refers to a spy. The other attestations refer to praetorian *speculatores* soldiers close to *Caesar*. In *Aug.* 74.1 Augustus rests in the house of one of his *speculatores*. In *Calig.* 44.2 the *speculatores* act as Caligula's personal couriers after his Pyrrhic victory in Britain. In *Claud.* 35.1 the protective role of Caesar towards these praetorian *speculatores* is described and it is asserted that Claudius would not dare to go to a banquet without the protection of these soldiers and their spears. A similar situation is recounted in *Galb.* 18.1, in which Galba was nearly wounded by the spear of one of his *speculatores* under the pressure of the crowd. In *Oth.* 5.2 Otho's strategy to recruit *speculatores* to his cause is narrated. Another attestation occurs in Sextus Pompeius Festus, *Verb. Sign.* 69 L (II CE) who in his grammar or dictionary of Latin words provides a definition of *speculator* in comparison with *explorator*: *speculator hostilia silentio perspicit, explorator pacata clamore cognoscit*.

Until 98 CE the praetorian *speculatores* were in charge of protecting the emperor⁴⁵. This changed with Trajan, who in 98 CE promoted the *equites singulares* as the imperial guard (Suetonius, *Claud.* 25.1)⁴⁶. During the third century the *speculatores* were replaced in these functions by the *frumentarii*⁴⁷. However, multiple attestations continue to appear on stelae and funerary inscriptions referring to the *speculatores*, although their functions were by that time different⁴⁸.

⁴¹ CIL 5.5071 (I CE, Italy). CIL 6.1921 (1-50 CE, Rome). CIL 5.6597 (I CE, Italy). CIL 6.2660 (31-70 CE, Rome). AE 2008.855 (1-50 CE, Italy). CIL 6.2755 (81-100 CE, Rome).

⁴² AE 1956.75 (I BCE, Italy). CIL 9.7 (61-100 CE, Italy). CIL 13.6884 (1-30 CE, Germania). AE 1982.164 (1-50 CE, Italy). CIL 11.395 (66 CE, Italy).

⁴³ Clauss 1973: 52.

⁴⁴ The only instance in Tacitus where *speculatores* is used for covert espionage operations, according to Austin and Rankov 1995: 56.

⁴⁵ After 69 CE, there is no indication they acted as bodyguards for the emperor. Speidel 1994: 29, 152. Trajan replaced them by the *hastilarii* (spearmen).

⁴⁶ Sheldon 2005: 167.

⁴⁷ The evolution of the role of the *frumentarii* is developed in McCunn 2019.

⁴⁸ Crimi 2012: 496-497.

From the epigraphic evidence it is clear that the *speculatores* diminished in importance towards the end of the first century and into the second century. We have 50 inscriptions mentioning the *speculatores* the first half of the 2nd century, but we know of only 15 inscriptions however from the second half of the 2nd century and the 3rd century onwards⁴⁹. This phenomenon is striking because the number of other praetorian inscriptions remains largely consistent until the end of the 3rd century. the number of *speculatores* did not decrease, but the importance of their office did. No longer did they have the special function they had fulfilled in the first century⁵⁰. From the middle of the 2nd century onwards, it became increasingly common for the emperors no longer to reside in Rome. Thus, the legions themselves took over the protection of the emperor. The organizational differences between the *speculatores* and the other praetorian soldiers are no longer perceptible in the 2nd and 3rd centuries. By this time we know from inscriptions that the *speculatores* were fully integrated into the individual *cohortes praetoriae*⁵¹. Alfred von Domaszewski has shown that the *speculatores* of the legions in the 2nd and 3rd centuries belonged to the governor's *officium*⁵² and that they acted as bailiffs or judicial officers⁵³.

4.4 Overview

Of the 70 attestations of the 1st century BCE, 65 appear in literary texts. Of these 70 attestations, 25 refer to Roman *speculatores*, 23 to soldiers related to military intelligence and 22 with the meaning of observer, spy, scout. In Julius Caesar's works, the word *speculatores* refers to soldiers in his army (9x). Livy is the most prolific witness to the use of the word with 34 attestations: 17 are for soldiers, 7 for Roman *speculatores* and 10 with other meanings. Only four inscriptions and one coin of Mark Antony are attested with this meaning in this century. In the 1st century CE, we have 51 attestations: 36 in inscriptions, one papyrus and 14 in literary texts. Two attestations by Seneca are significant, where *speculatores* perform executions by sword. Of these 51 attestations, 39 refer to Roman *speculatores* soldiers, 7 to soldiers performing military intelligence activities for other armies and 5 to observers or spies. In the 2nd century CE, 86 attestations are identified: 65 in inscriptions and 21 in literary texts, Tacitus and Suetonius being significant. 80 of these 86 attestations refer to Roman *speculatores* soldiers.

In summary, the word *speculator* in the context of military language refers in the 1st century CE to a *speculator*, mainly praetorian, belonging to the emperor's guard. The service of these soldiers is limited to Rome⁵⁴. *Speculator* may also refer to a *speculator* of the legions, with functions relating to military intelligence and acting as courier on some occasions. These attestations are scarce, limited to Tacitus *Ann.* 2.73.1 and 5 inscriptions. It appears, therefore, that Rome or Italy would be the most plausible place for use of this word.

⁴⁹ Attestations of *speculatores* of the legions. II CE: AE 2007.1363 (101-200 CE, Philadelphia), CIL 7.24 (101-150 CE, Britannia), CIL 3.1914 (1-150 CE, Dalmatia), AE 1914.75 (51-150 CE, Dalmatia), CIL 3.2910 (1-150 CE, Dalmatia); AE 1977.811 (180-192 CE, Galatia). ILJug 3.1419 (101-200 CE, Moesia). CIL 3.10480 (101-200 CE, Pannonia). Spalj 1, p. 7 (51-150 CE, Pannonia). CIL 6.3562 (117-150 CE, Rome). AE 1991.268 (151-200, Rome). CIL 3.13574 (II CE, Koptos).

⁵⁰ Clauss 1973: 56-57.

⁵¹ Clauss 1973: 56.

⁵² Austin and Rankov 1995: 151.

⁵³ Domaszewski and Dobson 1981: 32, 63, 73-74.

⁵⁴ After Tacitus (55-120 CE) – and this means by the time of the year of the four emperors – no writer mentions the *speculatores* in their capacity as bodyguards of the emperor.

The following table presents a summary of the data presented. The first column presents the number of times the word *speculator* appears in an author (second column), the third column the years in which that author lived. The fourth column presents the number of attestations referring to Roman *speculatores* soldiers, the fifth the number of attestations in which the word *speculator* refers to a soldier of another army and the sixth the attestations related with the meanings: observer, scout, explorer, spy.

Number	Attestations	Years	Roman <i>speculatores</i> soldiers.	Soldiers	Observer/ Spy
70	I BCE		25	23	22
9	Cicero, <i>Nat. d.</i> 1.83; 2.140; <i>Dom.</i> 8; <i>Man.</i> 19; <i>Verr.</i> 2.5.164-166 (4x); <i>Div. Q. Caec.</i> 16	106-43 BCE		1	8
4	Julius Caesar, <i>BGall.</i> 2.11; 5.49; <i>BCiv.</i> 3.66.1; 3.67.1	100-44 BCE	4		
10	Julius Caesar, <i>BHisp.</i> 13; 20; 22; 28.1 and 38 (2x); <i>BAfr.</i> 12.1; 31.4; 35; 37.1	40 BCE	9	1	
2	Sallust, <i>Jug.</i> 101; 106	86-34 BCE		2	
1	Nepos, <i>Alcib.</i> 8	100-25 BCE		1	
1	Vergil, <i>Aeneid.</i> 12.346	70-19 BCE		1	
2	Ovidius, <i>Am.</i> 1.9.16; <i>Trist.</i> 3.9.10.	43-17 BCE			2
1	Sextus Propertius, <i>Elegies</i> 2.29b	54-16 BCE			2
1	Vitruvius, <i>De Architectura</i> 10.16	80-15 BCE			1
34	Livy, <i>Ab urbe condita</i>	59 BCE-17 CE	7	17	10
1	Coin: RRC 544/12	32-31 BCE	1		
4	Inscriptions		4		
51	I CE		39	7	5
5	Seneca, <i>Ben.</i> 25; <i>Nat.</i> 4b.6.2; <i>Dial.</i> 5.36.2; <i>Ira</i> 1.18.4; 3.36.2	4 BCE-65 CE	2		3
1	Lucanus, <i>Pharsalia</i> 8.472	39-65 CE		1	
1	Pliny, <i>Nat.</i> 11.19	23-79 CE			1
2	Valerius Maximus, <i>Facta et Dicta Memorabilia</i> 3.7.1c; 7.4	I CE		1	1
5	Q. Curtius Rufus, <i>Hist.</i> 3.8.17-18; 4.9.1; 4.10.9; 6.4.14	I CE		5	
1	Papyrus ChLA. 1.7.a.b.9	81-90 CE	1		
36	Inscriptions		36		
86	II CE		80	2	4
1	Silius Italicus, <i>Punica</i> 1.679	26-101 CE			1
11	Tacitus, <i>Ann.</i> 2.12.1; <i>Hist.</i> 1.24.2; 1.25.1; 1.27.2; 1.31.1; 1.35.2; 1.43.2; 2.11.3; 2.33.3; 2.73.1; 3.43.2	55-120 CE	10		1
6	Suetonius, <i>Aug.</i> 27.4; <i>Aug.</i> 74.1; <i>Calig.</i> 44.2; <i>Claud.</i> 35.1; <i>Galb.</i> 18.1; <i>Oth.</i> 5.2	70-126	5		1
1	Sextus Pompeius Festus, <i>Verb. Sign.</i> 69 L	II CE		1	
1	Florus, <i>Epit.</i> 2.17.7.13	II CE		1	
1	Apuleius, <i>Metamorphoses</i> 4.6	124-170 CE			1
50	Inscriptions	100-150 CE	50		
15	Inscriptions	150-200 CE	15		

5 The narrative context in which the word appears. The narrative world

What does the word σπεκουλάτωρ mean in its Markan context? To answer this question, σπεκουλάτωρ must be analyzed first, in the context of the pericope in which it appears, second in relation to Mark's use of other Latin words, and third, in the context of the situation of language contact between Greek and Latin in the 1st century CE.

An analysis of this pericope (Mk 6.17-29) reveals some surprising characteristics. It is the only story in Mark's gospel in which Jesus is neither the protagonist nor appears with his disciples. Its literary genre has also attracted attention⁵⁵. Its literary history has also sparked discussion. Some commentators propose that it comes from a previous source that Mark reworked. Others suggest a Semitic influence or that its origins were an Aramaic source⁵⁶. On the other hand, other scholars point to Roman colouring in the story⁵⁷. In the description of the characters, Mark speaks of the τοῖς μεγιστᾶσιν αὐτοῦ καὶ τοῖς χιλιάρχοις καὶ τοῖς πρώτοις τῆς Γαλιλαίας⁵⁸. In this context, therefore, one can infer that the σπεκουλάτωρ is one of the soldiers under the command of the χιλιάρχοι, although it is Herod who directly addresses him⁵⁹, and so possibly he was a soldier of Herod's personal guard.

Within its Markan context, the scene parallels Jesus's trial before Pilate and his execution by a σπεῖρα and a centurion⁶⁰. Both John and Jesus are put to death by a ruler who recognizes their goodness, but who is described as giving into pressure. In both scenes the soldiers ordered by Herod and Pilate to carry out the executions of John and Jesus each have a Roman name.

At the level of the language-contact between Greek and Latin, Mark's use of several Latin words indicates that it was written in a place with a high degree of language contact. A number of reasons can be given. 1) Mark's use of σπεκουλάτωρ is in keeping with his use of words such as δηνάριον, καῖσαρ, κεντυρίων, κῆνσος, etc., therefore his use of the word σπεκουλάτωρ is not isolated or unconscious. 2) Mark's gospel has a large number of Latin words for a 1st century CE text⁶¹. Mark's frequency of Latinisms is very high. In a work of 11,133 words Mark has 12 loanwords, while Polybius presents 33 in a work of 316,866 words⁶². In the second century Epictetus has 20 loanwords in a work of 74,992 words, and Plutarch 180 loanwords in a work of 1,100,000 words⁶³. According to Daris there appear only 9 Latin loanwords in the 1st century BCE in the 1,085 papyri found and in the 1st century CE in 2,478 papyri⁶⁴. Therefore

⁵⁵ Legend (Bultmann), anecdote (Dibelius), court tale (K. Berger), novella (Lohmeyer), court legend (Theissen). Cf. Collins 2007: 304-305.

⁵⁶ βασιλεύς could be a calque of the word 'king' in Hebrew and Aramaic instead of tetrarch. It could also be a popular usage or politeness.

⁵⁷ For Hoehner, a single word cannot prove the Roman origin of such a semitized pericope. Hoehner 1972: 120. For Brandon, the use of σπεκουλάτωρ denotes that the pericope is of Roman origin. Brandon 1967: 268-269, n. 6.

⁵⁸ The typological characterisation of Antipas in this passage is described in Smith 2006.

⁵⁹ In fact in Mk 6.16 Herod is presented as the author of the execution: 'But when Herod heard this, he said, John, whom I beheaded, has been raised from the dead!' (Mk 6.16).

⁶⁰ McVann 2008. Hooker 1993: 158-159 and 378.

⁶¹ 'The remarkable thing about the Gospel of Mark is that it contains not only more Aramaic formulae than any other original Greek literary text, but also more Latinisms. Such an accumulation of Latinisms is unusual in comparison with other writings' in Hengel 1985: 29.

⁶² Dickey 2023. 20 according to Dubuisson 1985: 55.

⁶³ Cf. Dickey 2023.

⁶⁴ Daris 1971. Also in Dickey 2012: 67 and Dickey 2023: 655-657.

Mark represents the highest frequency of Latinisms for a literary work⁶⁵. In this sense, Mark's use of Latinisms fits with the oral register of the Koine language of the popular classes in Rome⁶⁶. 3) Mark not only presents the highest frequency of Latinisms (some of them already integrated in Koine Greek such as *δηνάριον*, *καῖσαρ*, *κεντυρίων*, *λεγιών* and *μόδιος*) but also presents several cases of incipient loanwords (*ξέστης*, *πραιτώριον* and *κῆνσος*⁶⁷) and nonce-borrowings, so that he is the first witness of *σπεκουλάτωρ*, *κοδράντης*, and the verb *φραγελλώω*, which is very significant, since most of the borrowings are nouns. 4) Mark explains Greek words by means of Latin words (*λεπτὰ δύο, ὃ ἐστὶν κοδράντης* Mk 12.42 and *τῆς αὐλῆς, ὃ ἐστὶν πραιτώριον* 15.16), a behavior which fits with Rome⁶⁸, the place where makes sense to explain 'two little coins' as one *quadrans*.

6 The historical context of Mark's σπεκουλάτωρ. The real world

To whom does Mark refer by the word *σπεκουλάτωρ*? There are two possibilities, either a legionary *speculator* or a soldier of Antipas whom Mark describes by that name. But before discussing these two possibilities, it is useful to know the military troops that were stationed in Palestine and Syria⁶⁹. Before the first Jewish war there were three types of troops in the region. First, the Roman legions, made up of Roman citizens and speaking mainly Latin. The legions III *Gallica*, VI *Ferrata*, X *Fretensis* and XII *Fulminata* were stationed in Syria, close to the Parthian border⁷⁰. Secondly, there were auxiliary troops of the Roman army, non-citizen soldiers serving the government of Rome⁷¹. They were of two types: *cohors* (*σπεῖρα*) infantry troops and *ala* (*εἰλη*) mounted troops. Josephus speaks of 5 cohorts and one *ala* in Judea (*A.J.* 19.365 and *B.J.* 2.52)⁷². The cohorts stationed there were *Cohortes I-V Sebastenorum* and *Ala Sebastenorum*. They were troops that had been mostly recruited from Sebaste and Caesarea Maritima (*A.J.* 19.365). Josephus emphasizes that they were primarily Syrian and Greek troops and would undoubtedly have spoken Greek. The third type of troops were those of the client kings, such as the Nabataean troops, those of Herod the Great, the army of Philip and that of Antipas, etc. We have little information about them, since in his description of the Jewish War, Josephus focuses on the legions and there is little mention of the auxiliary troops or royal troops.

6.1 The legionary *speculatores*

Mark could be referring to a *speculator* of the legions stationed in Syria who would be required to serve Antipas occasionally. Tacitus recalls how the *speculatores* met Vitellius with news from his legions in Syria (Tacitus, *Hist.* 2.73.1, occurring 69 CE). But is it plausible that in the year 30 there was a Roman *speculator* alongside Antipas? This would be more tenable if event

⁶⁵ Dickey 2023 does not record Mark's occurrences of *δηνάριον*, *κῆνσος*, *λεγιών*, *μόδιος* and *πραιτώριον*, so this high frequency cannot be perceived in her book.

⁶⁶ Kaimio 1979: 52 and 172. 'Greek at Rome' in Swain 2002: 130-136. According to Mullen 2011: 533, 'Latin-Greek bilingualism was not restricted to elite society. Trade, slavery and intermarriage meant that both Latin and Greek were spoken at lower social levels in numerous communities'.

⁶⁷ *ξέστης* (BGU 16.2669, I BCE, Egypt) and *πραιτώριον* (Phil. 1.13, Acts 23.35, Jn 18.28, in several papyri from the beginning of the 2nd century CE, e.g. P.Oxy. 58.3917 (100-125 CE)). Prior to Mark there is only one attestation of *κῆνσος* (ABSA 12, I BCE, Bizye) and in later attestations *κῆνσος* always has the meaning of census and never of tax. *κοδράντης* only in IC 2.11.3 (I BCE) and SEG 55.821 form 6.1.

⁶⁸ 'The decisive point is that Mark explains Greek by Latin'. Zahn 1909: 503-504.

⁶⁹ Schürer, Vermes, Millar, Goodman and Black 2014: 363-366. Zeichmann 2018a: 93-112.

⁷⁰ Grainger 2017: 60-69.

⁷¹ The Roman auxiliaries troops in Syria are detailed in Saddington 2009: 309-310 and Grainger 2017: 69-75.

⁷² There is no evidence of any Italian auxiliary unit in pre-War Judaea (Josephus, *A.J.* 19.365).

occurred in Machaerus (Josephus, *A.J.* 18.119) than in Galilee. But if the incident did indeed take place in Machaerus (Perea), it makes little sense that a legionary *speculator* of the *Legio XII Fulminata*, stationed in Raphanea (Syria), on the border with the Parthians⁷³, and 464 km far from Machaerus, could have been present at the feast of Antipas. The presence of some soldiers with Roman names in Herod's army could be another factor to consider; *Volumnius* was the general of Herod's army (Josephus, *B.J.* 1.535; *A.J.* 16.332) and *Rufus* and *Gratus* commanded the royal cavalry and infantry respectively (*B.J.* 2.52, 74; *A.J.* 17.266). The fact that they have Roman names does not mean that they were Roman citizens, but it was common for ex-centurions to be offered to auxiliary troops in the provinces⁷⁴. A similar situation could have occurred in Antipas's army.

6.2 The σπεκουλάτωρ as a soldier of Herod's army

The other possibility is that this σπεκουλάτωρ was a soldier of Herod's army, who was in charge of different functions, among them executions, and was called σπεκουλάτωρ by Mark to give his audience a better understanding of the kind of soldier being spoken of, and also to emphasise Antipas' collaboration with Rome⁷⁵. That Herod Antipas had an army at his disposal is beyond doubt, for this is noted by both Mark and Flavius Josephus, although we have very little information about it⁷⁶. It is therefore worth highlighting first some aspects of Herod's army, which is what we have most information about. Herod the Great had a large army, which played an important role in his rise to the throne and in his power (*A.J.*, 17.198; *B.J.*, 1.672)⁷⁷. On some of his coins (Hendin 2010 §1169) a military helmet, symbol of his army (or military might) and power⁷⁸ is represented, and on others a shield (Hendin 2010 §1170). This army would have been passed to Archelaus after his death⁷⁹ and when Judea became a Roman prefecture dependent on the province of Syria, Archelaus' troops became Roman auxiliary troops (*auxilia*)⁸⁰.

Focusing on Antipas' army, Mark notes that he was assembled with his χιλίαρχος (Mk 6.21), a technical term for the commanders of his troops. Josephus' silence about Antipas' army may indicate that he had few sources for the period between the end of Nicholas of Damascus' source and the events of the Jewish War. We do know from Josephus that Antipas' army was defeated by the Nabataean king Aretas IV following Antipas' divorce from Aretas' daughter (*A.J.* 18.114). According to Josephus, the defeat was interpreted by the people as a punishment for the death of John the Baptist (*A.J.* 18.116). Josephus notes that part of Philip's army that had joined Antipas' army after Philip's death, deserted him in the war with Aretas (*A.J.* 18.114). We also know that Antipas was accused of planning a revolt by Agrippa I before the emperor Caligula, on account of Antipas' large arsenal (*A.J.* 18.251). This accusation

⁷³ In the years 40 BCE-62 CE, *Legio XII Fulminata* was stationed in Raphanea, *X Fretensis* in Cyrrhus (moved to Zeugma in 18 CE), *VI Ferrata* in Laodikeia and *III Gallica* in Antioch. Grainger 2017: 63.

⁷⁴ Cf. Mason 2016: 36. In the years after Actium large numbers of Roman soldiers were discharged by Octavian. Given the fact that client kings needed efficient armed forces these soldiers could be Roman-trained officers. Cf. Gracey 1986: 314.

⁷⁵ Zeichmann points out that σπεκουλάτωρ is more a term of Mark than of Antipas. Zeichmann 2018b: 58.

⁷⁶ The coins of Antipas and Philip did not contain any military elements. 'The military forces of the region remained basically the same from the reign of Herod, through his successors Archelaus, Antipas, Philip, Agrippa I and II, down to the end of the Jewish War'. Roth 2004: 5.

⁷⁷ Gracey 1996; Rocca and Hook 2009.

⁷⁸ Ariel and Fontanille 2012: 107-109.

⁷⁹ A military helmet also appears on coins of Archelaus (Hendin 2010 §1196), and on two other coins a war galley is represented (Hendin 2010 §1194).

⁸⁰ Kraeling 1942: 266; Kennedy 1996: 795. Its army would be made up of an equal proportion of Jews and non-Jews. Zeichmann 2018a: 95; Rocca 2008: 133-196; Wilker 2007; cf. 'Sebastenes' in Mason 2016: 36.

ultimately led to his fall and banishment. It is possible that Caligula feared an alliance between Antipas and the Parthians (*A.J.* 18.250), as Antipas played a significant role in the defense of Rome's frontier with the Parthians. Finally it could be underlined that Antipas had been educated in Rome (*A.J.* 17.20), had traveled several times to Rome and would have known the praetorian *speculatores* soldiers well.

In this second case the word σπεκουλάτωρ would evoke, in a Greco-Roman discursive community, a praetorian *speculator* rather than a legionary *speculator*, particularly in view of the actions carried out. We have testimonies of clandestine arrests and executions in Rome carried out at the sword of *speculatores*, although executions were not their primary function (Seneca). Two options arise in this case. 1) σπεκουλάτωρ is a word that is part of the vocabulary of the Markan discursive community, which implies a context of high language contact between Latin and Greek. Mark would be using it because it allows him to specify what kind of soldier performs the execution, being more specific than σκοπός, κατάσκοπος or δήμιος. This usage makes sense from a sociolinguistic point of view since he is using a word from another language as a specification⁸¹. 2) It could be an interference, a word from the donor language (Latin) appearing in a discourse in the recipient language (Greek), which is an unintentional and in many cases unconscious process. This use could reflect that Mark learned the meaning of several words from Latin attaching them to his Greek idiolect. In this sense, Mark also makes use of other Latin borrowings pertaining to the military register, such as κεντυρίων. Although κεντυρίων was a word already integrated into koine Greek in the first century CE, it does not appear in any literary text apart from Mark and a gloss in Polybius (*Hist.* 6.24.5), who uses it to explain the Latin name given by the Romans to centurions. Therefore Mark's use of σπεκουλάτωρ is in line with his use of κεντυρίων, both linguistically and narratively. This use would prevent the use of σπεκουλάτωρ from being seen as an interference.

From the above analysis it seems considerably more likely that Mark is referring to a soldier of Antipas' personal guard whom he describes as a σπεκουλάτωρ as a way of allowing him to specify his functions, which fit in with those performed by the praetorian *speculatores* in Rome⁸².

7 The Greek semantic field related with soldiers

Why did Mark use a Latin word when he had other Greek words related to the semantic field of soldiers at his disposal? The author has used σπεκουλάτωρ in Mk 6.27 to designate this character, but he had a wide semantic field to refer to a soldier, such as στρατιώτης, which he uses in Mk 15.16. Moreover, in the LXX there is a wide range of words to refer to a soldier such as: μαχητής (*Amos* 2.14), όπλίτης (*Num.* 32.21), πολεμιστής (*Num.* 31.27), στρατιώτης (*2 Macc.* 5.12), and ίππεύς (*Gen.* 49.17). The semantic field is enormous, including words such as the already noted στρατιώτης as well as technical words such as ίππεύς (horseman), κορυνηφόροι (standard-bearer), άσπιστήρ (soldier with shield) or αιχμητής (spearmen). For

⁸¹ When a language has a word to cover a certain meaning and it borrows another one, one of the terms tends to undergo semantic specialization and become restricted in meaning. Romaine 1995: 66.

⁸² According to Collins, '*Speculator* was also used to designate one of the *principales* (attendants) of a provincial governor. It is used analogously here of a member of Herod Antipas's staff, whose responsibility included executions'. Collins 2007: 314, following Hoehner 1972: 119-120. But this opinion is not correct, since *speculatores* only appear as members of the governor's *officium* in the third century.

scouts and spies in an army, Greek has words such as σκόπος, ἐπίσκοπος, and κατασκόπος⁸³. In Polybius (*Hist.* 14.3.7), for example, the term κατασκόπος is used to refer to scouts investigating the enemy camp. The words σκόπος and κατασκόπος are used in Greek as calques to refer specifically to soldiers *speculatores*. Dionysius of Halicarnassus (60-7 BCE) makes use of the term κατασκόπος to refer to *speculatores*, though also to *procursatores* and *exploratores*⁸⁴. Plutarch uses σκόπος to refer to both *exploratores* (*Crass.* 23.2; *Marc.* 29.8-11) and *speculatores*⁸⁵. Plutarch uses κατάσκοπος to refer to Greek scout soldiers (*Eum.* 9.5) and a spy (*Galb.* 13.1), and uses κατασκοπήν to refer to surveillance and spying soldiers (*Sert.* 3.2). Words such as δορυφόρος, δορυφόρημα, or ἐπίσκοπος are also used to refer to scouts or spies⁸⁶ and σωματοφύλαξ is used for bodyguards. If Mark had wanted to refer to an official executioner, such as the *carnifex*, he could have used δήμιος or ἀποκεφαλίστης.

In conclusion, Mark makes use of a Latin word, not attested in koine Greek in the 1st century. Mark had other words at his disposal to refer to that soldier, whether he was a Roman soldier *speculator* or not. Furthermore, this analysis of the Greek semantic field allows us to qualify the sociolinguistic character of the word. σπεκουλάτωρ is a core borrowing (a word that duplicates an element that the recipient language already has in its word store⁸⁷). More specifically, it is a ‘reverse core borrowing’, a word borrowed from a less prestigious language (Latin) to replace a word that already existed in the native language (Greek)⁸⁸. Mark’s use of σπεκουλάτωρ does not correspond to either of the two most recognised functions of borrowing⁸⁹: lexical need and prestige, so its use must serve specific functions.

8 The effect of Mark’s σπεκουλάτωρ on his audience

What would the use of this word evoke in his audience? First, as it has been already pointed out σπεκουλάτωρ is a nonce-borrowing, specifically a reverse core borrowing and therefore had attracted the attention of the listeners. It would have struck Mark’s audience as odd and would only have been intelligible to those familiar with the Latin word. The use of a word from another language could be perceived as a barbarism, and distances Mark from the style of the elites (Aristotle, *Ret.* 3.1407a 20). This usage reflects a rather oral dialect and suggests a solidarity with the lower classes.

Second, in view of the attestations, it is most likely that the word σπεκουλάτωρ evoked in a Greco-Roman context a praetorian *speculator*, soldiers charged with the protection of the emperor, who were assigned missions of espionage, arrests and even executions. Most attestations of the Latin word *speculator* in the 1st and 2nd centuries refer to these praetorian *speculatores*. Two quotations from Seneca (and later, the *Digest*) refer to *speculatores* executing people. The actions of these praetorian *speculatores* were generally limited to Rome.

⁸³ Pritchett 1974: 129-130. κατασκόπος appears once in Homer, 22x in Herodotus, and 6x in Thucydides. Also in Aeneas the Tactician, Polybius, and Xenophon.

⁸⁴ κατάσκοπος in Dionysius of Halicarnassus, *Ant. rom.* 6.15.3; 8.37.2; 8.82.2; 8.86.2; 9.61.4.

⁸⁵ In Plutarch, *Pomp.* 68.3 the word σκόπος refers surely to Caesar’s *exploratores*, although later it is pointed out that there are other soldiers who confirm that information, which could be *speculatores*.

⁸⁶ σωματοφύλαξ translating *cubicularius* or *speculator* in Arrian, *Acies* 22-23 and Appian, *Hist. rom.* 20.57. Mason 1974: 90.

⁸⁷ Myers-Scotton 2006: 211-213.

⁸⁸ ‘Reverse core borrowing’ in Myers-Scotton 2006: 215-217. Moreover, σπεκουλάτωρ could be an example of ‘oral or vulgar’ borrowing as opposed to ‘written or learned’ borrowings coming from literary texts. Mullen 2011: 533.

⁸⁹ Poplack 2018: 58-60, 182, 204-205.

The word could also evoke a legionary *speculator* or a scout soldier of Antipas' army, but this use does not fit with the actions of the character in Mark's account.

Third, the effect of the use of σπεκουλάτωρ is similar to that occasioned by the use of κεντυρίων in the death of Jesus. The use of a Latin loanword reinforces the soldier's connection to the Roman Empire and makes present the force of the empire that executed Jesus and will go on to destroy the Temple and Jerusalem. The use of the word also recalls the events of the year of the four emperors, during which the praetorian *speculatores* played a determining role.

9 Mark's provenance

Can this word help to illuminate where Mark's gospel was written? It is worth noting that the provenance of Mark's gospel is a complex issue. Mark may have travelled and his idiolect need not reflect the place where he lives or the readership he addresses. The Latin words could reflect that he lived in a Roman colony or in any city with high language contact. Having stated this, and on the basis of the discussion above, it can be affirmed that the word σπεκουλάτωρ in Mk 6.27 evokes the Roman *speculatores* soldiers and fits with the city of Rome as the place of provenance of Mark's Gospel. Several reasons can be put forward.

First, in the 1st century most instances of the word *speculator* refer to the praetorian *speculatores* soldiers and point to Rome where carried out their actions. Evidence of the functions of the praetorian *speculatores* in inscriptions are only to be found in Rome. Moreover, the actions of Mark's character are consistent with the functions these praetorian *speculatores* developed. Therefore in the 1st century CE, the word σπεκουλάτωρ would evoke mainly the praetorian *speculator* soldiers who were the personal guard of the emperor and the protagonists of political events particularly in the Year of the Four Emperors. The resonances of the word in Rome in the years 68-70 CE must have been very significant and the impact of their actions in Rome still resonates with Tacitus and Suetonius in the 2nd century. Mark's use of the word σπεκουλάτωρ is consistent with his use of other Latin words to refer to military and administrative aspects of the Roman empire, such as κεντυρίων, πραιτώριον, καῖσαρ, and κῆνσος, which avoids thinking that σπεκουλάτωρ was merely an interference.

Second, the use of the word κοδράντης referring to the Roman coin *quadrans*, a coin that only circulated in the western part of the empire and not in Syria, where there is no attestation of the use of this coin or this word⁹⁰. Moreover, the use of *denarii* to explain the value of certain objects (Mk 6.37 and 14.5) would reflect the western part of the empire, when in Palestine and Syria one would expect tetradrachms⁹¹.

Third, several circumstances indicate that Mark was written in a place with a situation of high language contact, in a manner entirely compatible with Rome. 1) Mark's frequency of Latinisms represents the highest frequency of Latinisms for any surviving literary work, which fits with Rome⁹². In this sense, Mark's use of Latinisms fits with the oral register of the Koine

⁹⁰ Heuchert 2005: 30.

⁹¹ 'By the second century, the primary silver mint had moved from Phoenician Tyre to Syrian Antioch. These Antiochene tetradrachms were supplemented by a steady supply of Roman imperial *denarii*, which supposedly began to circulate in Palestine after the end of the First Jewish Revolt but are not in fact found in hoards with closing dates before the second century' in Goldman 2020: 213.

⁹² 'Numerous Latinisms point to an origin in Rome' in Hengel 1985: 29. 'The most likely place for Latinisms to predominate is in the city of Rome, where the Latin and Greek languages were closely intermingled as nowhere else at that time... It was in Rome most of all that the ordinary person was forced to deal with both

language of the popular classes in Rome⁹³. 2) Mark presents integrated loanwords, incipient loanwords, nonce-borrowings, and codeswitchings from Greek to Latin words. 3) The phenomenon of explaining Greek words by means of Latin words is not attested in the Greek corpus and fits with Rome.

By virtue of the reasons presented, especially the conjunction of the use of σπεκουλάτωρ and κοδράντης, we can postulate that the Gospel of Mark originated in the city of Rome.

10 Conclusion

In the 1st century, the word σπεκουλάτωρ only appears attested in the Gospel of Mark. It is a Latin word with several meanings, but in specifically military usage during the 1st century, it refers foremost to the praetorian *speculatores* charged with the protection of the emperor and secondarily to the *speculatores* of the legions, who fulfilled various functions relating to military intelligence and on certain occasions acted as couriers and messengers.

It is very likely that Mark chose this word to explain to his audience what kind of soldier had executed John the Baptist. This would have been a soldier similar to a *speculator*, who in the 1st century acted in Rome protecting the emperor and were charged with espionage and even covert assassinations. Mark's use of the word σπεκουλάτωρ is in line with his use of the word κεντυρίων. It is a *speculator* who murders John and it is a *centurio* who directed Jesus' execution.

In the first century, according to most inscriptions, papyri, and literary references, the *speculatores*' activities took place in the city of Rome. It is therefore the most plausible city for its use. The use of σπεκουλάτωρ along with κοδράντης (among other factors), would supports Rome as the probable context for the gospel's composition.

languages in daily life.' Incigneri 2003: 101-102. 'Still it must have been very natural for an author writing in Rome for Romans to employ Latin names for Latin things'. Zahn: 1909: 489.

⁹³ Kaimio 1979: 52, 172. 'Greek at Rome' in Swain 2002: 130-136. According to Mullen 2011: 533, 'Latin-Greek bilingualism was not restricted to elite society. Trade, slavery and intermarriage meant that both Latin and Greek were spoken at lower social levels in numerous communities'.

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